

Supplementary Information

In-plane anisotropic optical and mechanical properties of two-dimensional

MoO₃

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In order to explain the Angle-Resolved Polarized Raman Spectroscopy technique we provide the following Supplementary Figure 1a, in which is shown a scheme of the experimental set up used to obtain the data shown in Fig. 1. In Supplementary Figure 1b we show the laboratory coordinates, as dotted arrows, and the sample coordinates, as continuous arrows.

Supplementary Figure 1 (a) Schematic diagram of polarization configuration setup used for angle-resolved polarized Raman scattering spectroscopy, in which the incident light pass through a linear polarizer and reaching the sample, which is placed onto a rotating holder. The Raman scattered light is passed through the analyzer before entering the spectrometer. (b) Top view of the configuration, the laser and analyzer are set in parallel configuration (both are oriented in the same direction) and the grey curved arrow indicates the rotation of the sample with its axis with an angle β respect to the laboratory coordinates. Laboratory coordinates (xyz) are represented by black dotted arrows, and crystal coordinates are represented by black continuous arrows.

Supplementary Figure 2 Optical contrast of MoO₃ flake of thickness 24 nm, studied in the main text Fig. 4. Insets: Polar plot of refractive index (top right) and picture of the flake (bottom left), showing its axes and its respective crystal structure, scale bar is of 5 μm.

Supplementary Figure 3. AFM measurement of MoO₃ flake shown in Fig. 2b of main text. Scale bar is 10 μm.

Supplementary Figure 4 (a) Energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) -SEM map of a MoO₃ flake onto a Si substrate with 200 nm of Si₃N₄ capping layer, showing each element contribution. (b) SEM image showing the area in red, in which EDS measurement has been carried out, scale bar is of 5 μm. (c) EDS measurement showing N, O, Si and Mo peaks. Left part of the figure corresponds to a flake deposited on the substrate with all-dry deterministic placement and the right part corresponds to flakes directly grown on a Si₃N₄/Si substrate.

Supplementary Figure 5. Full Raman spectra of MoO_3 sample, pointed peaks belong to typical MoO_3 Raman spectrum,¹⁻³ except the one of 519 cm^{-1} belonging to Si. No signal arising from MoO_2 has been observed.

Supplementary Figure 6. (a) Raman spectra at 0° (blue), 45° (black) and 90° (red) angles with respect to the horizontal axis. A_g^c , B_{2g} and A_g^a Raman modes are highlighted with vertical dashed lines. Inset: Microscopy image of the sample placed in the initial position (0°) and the c and a axes, determined from the angle-resolved Raman measurements, are shown. (b) Polar plots, in light purple; and fittings, in dark purple, of angle-resolved normalized Raman intensities of the A_g^c (left), B_{2g} (middle) and A_g^a (right) modes. These measurements have been done using a 457nm laser wavelength and the same method as the one in Fig. 1. Note, MoO_3 Raman peaks have no dependence on the wavelength of laser used.

Supplementary Figure 7. Video caption of buckling metrology method applied on a MoO₃ flake onto PDMS substrate.

Theoretical Analysis

We have investigated the elastic response of the MoO₃ orthorhombic phase with crystal lattice $a = 3.969 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 14.425 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 3.761 \text{ \AA}$. Using DFT and the Quantum-Espresso package (thermo_pw) and norm-conserving pseudo potentials, we have calculated the elastic matrix (all elements in units of GPa)

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 110.50 & 27.32 & 34.60 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 27.32 & 42.05 & 32.22 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 34.60 & 32.22 & 243.57 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 38.80 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 59.47 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 30.93 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The stiffness matrix, S (1/GPa), the inverse of C , is,

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 0.01088128 & -0.00654958 & -0.00067912 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.0065496 & 0.03040684 & -0.00309197 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.00067909 & -0.00309199 & 0.00461108 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.02577902 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01681517 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.03232566 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

From this we can read the elastic coefficients along the principal axis:

Young moduli

$$E_a = 91.9 \text{ GPa}, E_c = 216.87 \text{ GPa}, \quad (3)$$

while the **Poisson's ratios** are

$$\nu_{ca} = 0.147, \nu_{ac} = 0.06 \quad (4)$$

Similar results are obtained with the ultra-soft pseudo potential.

Following the Reuss and Voigt approximations for polycrystalline materials we get

Voigt approximation:

Bulk modulus

$$B = 64.932164 \text{ GPa} \quad (5)$$

Young modulus

$$E = 111.302287 \text{ GPa} \quad (6)$$

Shear modulus

$$G = 45.829385 \text{ GPa} \quad (7)$$

Poisson Ratio

$$\nu = 0.21431 \quad (8)$$

Reuss approximation:

Bulk modulus

$$B = 39.591641 \text{ GPa} \quad (9)$$

Young modulus

$$E = 77.938993 \text{ GPa} \quad (10)$$

Shear modulus

$$G = 33.253128 \text{ GPa} \quad (11)$$

Poisson Ratio

$$\nu = 0.17190 \quad (12)$$

Voigt-Reuss-Hill average of the two approximations:

Bulk modulus

$$B = 52.261903 \text{ GPa} \quad (13)$$

Young modulus

$$E = 94.620640 \text{ GPa} \quad (14)$$

Shear modulus

$$G = 39.541257 \text{ GPa} \quad (15)$$

Poisson Ratio

$$\nu = 0.19648 \quad (16)$$

Supplementary references:

1. Chen, D. *et al.* Single-crystalline MoO₃ nanoplates: topochemical synthesis and enhanced ethanol-sensing performance. *J. Mater. Chem.* **21**, 9332 (2011).
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3. Dagar, J. *et al.* Application of 2D-MoO₃ nano-flakes in organic light emitting diodes: effect of semiconductor to metal transition with irradiation. *RSC Adv.* **5**, 8397–8403 (2015).